

Research Translation Strategy 2025 - 30

Acknowledgement of Country

AuScope Acknowledges the Traditional Custodians and first Earth scientists of the lands, waterways and skies across the Australian continent, including where our team lives, learns and shares knowledge.

We admire their long and continuing connection to Country¹ over tens of thousands of years. We are grateful to walk alongside the longest, continuous living cultures in the world. In the spirit of Reconciliation, and towards equity in Earth systems, we seek to build relationships with Indigenous scientists and communities and centre their approaches to - and Knowledges in - our work. We pay our deepest respects to all Aboriginal and/or Torres Strait Islander Elders, past and present.

Above: Professor Bradley Moggridge, Kamilaroi Scientist, stands on the edge of Mount Vesuvius in the JR Academy in 2024, an Indigenous-led science mentoring experience for Indigenous students worldwide, including Australia and Aotearoa New Zealand. AuScope supported this initiative via its ANZIC program.

“In the words of my ancestors to say hello and what is your intention? I say Yaama.”²

Professor Brad Moggridge, University of Technology Sydney

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Cover image: AuScope team members hand a baton over on Wurundjeri Country.

1. Common Ground (2021): <https://bit.ly/3F7tSYR>
2. Springer Nature Link (2024): <https://bit.ly/3SZZfaZ>

Introduction

AuScope supports Australia’s ‘laboratory’ for Earth and geospatial science, enabling scientists to generate knowledge about Earth processes, including resource systems and natural hazards across the Australian continent and beyond. Its national and global context is shifting, with Australia now facing significant, intersecting and rapidly evolving risks relating to climate change mitigation and adaptation, natural disasters, water scarcity, defence, sovereign capability and more.

The impact of these challenges on Country and planetary health¹ is palpable now and will continue into the decades ahead.² As such, ‘investing in national research infrastructure (NRI) to catalyse and accelerate the research needed to address these challenges has never been more important.’³

About AuScope

AuScope Limited (AuScope) is a non-profit organisation funded by the Department of Education (DE) through the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS). We build and operate national research infrastructure (NRI) for the Earth and geospatial sciences. Our university and government agency partners around Australia provide researchers with specialist tools, data, software, and expertise for subsurface studies. This work can benefit people across academia, government, industry, and communities through critical minerals discovery, natural hazards monitoring, fundamental Earth and planetary science discovery and outreach. Since 2007, AuScope has delivered national benefits, including precise positioning systems and resource discovery, with an estimated \$15 return for every \$1 invested⁴.

In the AuScope 10-Year Strategy 2020-2030⁵, AuScope outlines its Vision to enable a sustainable, resilient nation through predictive geoscience. It also states its Mission is to build an integrated, collaborative research platform. Finally, it states its Goals to enhance (1) NRI, including (2) data, (3) community, (4) culture, (5) Indigenous engagement, (6) Industry engagement and (7) international engagement.

Guiding AuScope’s work

Every five years, the Australian government undertakes a road mapping process to ensure that Australia’s NRI remains relevant and responsive to the needs of the national and research sector. The latest instance is the 2021 NRI Roadmap (2021 Roadmap)³, which focusses on long-term national benefits, strategic international partnerships, and a challenge-oriented approach to solving real-world (economic, societal and environmental) problems through research translation and commercialisation processes.

It outlines key challenges for Australia in the years and decades ahead in resource technologies, clean energy, climate, defence, space, and frontier technologies. AuScope is proud to address many of these challenges already.

Aside from the 2021 Roadmap, AuScope follows federal government policies, strategies and guidelines, including Australia’s National Science and Research Priorities (that centres Indigenous Knowledge Systems; see the diagram on page 23) (2024), Australia’s National Science Statement (2024), the Future Made in Australia agenda (2024), the Working for Women: A Strategy for Gender Equality (2024), the Pathway to Diversity in STEM Review (2024), the National Reconstruction Fund (2023), the Critical Technologies Statement (2023) and Australia’s Economic Accelerator (2022).

Climate change features prominently across all of these policies. In particular, the National Science Statement highlights climate action as crucial for Australia’s future prosperity. Recent data show that most Australians have experienced climate-related disasters⁶ and that high emissions scenarios could cost the country \$94 billion annually by 2060².

Adapting at AuScope for impact

Through the 2021 Roadmap and NCRIS 2025 Guidelines⁷, the Australian Government (through DE) encourages AuScope to make system-wide enhancements, build on strong foundations, and plan for a step-change in its research translation through targeted investment in translation research infrastructure (TRI). This TRI includes facilities, instruments, data, technology and expertise (workforce). It aims to boost industry engagement, strengthen Australia’s sovereign research capability, and make NRI useful and used by industry, government and community end-users. A recent DE survey⁸ highlights TRI priorities for NCRIS, including capability, end-user access, governance, data and security, and standards. This AuScope Research Translation Strategy 2025-30 (Strategy) aims to help the AuScope team (including participants of AuScope funded Projects) collaboratively address DE needs.

Pictured: Examples of Earth science applications underpinning Australia’s resilient future that AuScope NRI does or could underpin. Image: AuScope; Design By Bird. Noun Project icons (CC BY 3.0) by Lucas Helle (solar and battery farm), monkik (environmental monitoring), Lizzy Gregory (wind farm) BEJOUN (geothermal energy), and Symbolon (wave energy).

1. Capon (2020): <https://bit.ly/42xZyys>
2. Climate Council (2021): <https://bit.ly/43V2szs>
3. Department of Education (2022): <https://bit.ly/42rNDSv>
4. Lateral Economics (2016): <https://bit.ly/3Dz6Upy>
5. AuScope (2020): www.auscope.org.au/strategy
6. Climate Council (2023): <https://bit.ly/4jCs21a>
7. Department of Education (2025): <https://bit.ly/3FCfUPo>
8. Department of Education (2025): <https://bit.ly/4ku8GMI>

What is research translation?

Research translation is the widely understood process of converting research outputs - including AuScope-supported research facilities, instruments, data, software and knowledge - into demonstrable policy, business or community outcomes.^{1,2,3}

Below: CSIRO's Impact Framework¹ adapted visually to highlight people, pathways and stages of research translation that are relevant for AuScope as a research enabler. As CSIRO notes, 'for the sake of simplicity, the model depicts a simple linear process, but science is serendipitous and agile in action, with feedback loops and engagement at all stages.'

AuScope research inputs include resources and staff. AuScope research activities include any operational activity. AuScope research outputs include facilities, equipment, data, software and knowledge. Image credits (left to right) to Curtin University, AuScope, Jarred Lloyd Larisa Medenis and AuScope.

'If research outputs do not translate, they will not achieve research impact.'

— CoE in Treatable Traits

Overview

Research translation, also known as 'knowledge translation', 'knowledge transfer', 'knowledge exchange', 'knowledge mobilisation', and 'research to action', is central to CSIRO's Impact Framework¹, to which DE, and thus, AuScope subscribe.

Former Australian Chief Scientist Dr Cathy Foley offers a helpful metaphor for research translation: the relay race, where people 'hand the baton over' from academia to government, industry and community. AuScope or researcher users can lead this process. It can be active (with the AuScope team and users helping end-users gain value from AuScope for their policy, industry or community development work) or passive (with end-users finding and using AuScope research outputs independently). All pathways are valuable.

Readiness Levels

Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) are a valuable tool for assessing and communicating the maturity of R&D projects, from theoretical concepts (TRL 1) to operating systems, processes, products, services, or tools (TRL 9)⁴. Societal Readiness Levels (SRLs) are broadly equivalent to TRLs and used to assess the maturation of a social project, a technology, a product, a process, an intervention, or an innovation in society⁵. AuScope can benefit from considering how its Projects can scale along the TRL and SRL pathways towards research impact. Several NCRIS organisations use this approach in their work.

'I knew my [semiconductor] research was a potential game changer. But back then... the job of a scientist was to publish a paper. This was the end point. And there was no concept of passing the baton to someone else. I published the findings and moved on. Fortunately, the research baton was picked up, and eventually a Japanese team worked out how to create an LED with nitrides. [They] won a Nobel Prize for the invention. And LEDs, of course, are now the world's major form of lighting. With the benefit in hindsight, you might describe that as a brutal lesson in lost opportunities! Not only for me, but for Australia.'⁶

Dr Cathy Foley

AuScope research outcomes are demonstrable shifts in policy, business practice or community practice. AuScope research impact is, as CSIRO explains, 'an effect on, change or benefit to the economy, society and/or environment, beyond those contributions to academic knowledge.' Both are enabled, in some way(s), by AuScope.

1. CSIRO (2020): <https://bit.ly/4jdwSBV>
2. Australian Research Council (2021): <https://bit.ly/4jaDAIX>
3. World Health Organisation (2020): <https://bit.ly/3YyyI7U>
4. NOAA (2025): <https://bit.ly/4cBJN2I>
5. Innovation Fund Denmark (2019): <https://bit.ly/4jwcWtv>
6. Australian Press Club (2021): <https://bit.ly/4jy00n9>

Discovery with AuScope Communities

AuScope has been driving research translation since its inception in 2007. Now, equipped with valuable insights from AuScope Communities across sectors, AuScope seeks to translate more holistically, strategically and significantly.

AuScope impact to date

AuScope has been creating value for end-users in government, industry and community in small and large ways for almost two decades. Examples of successful AuScope research translation include:

- A key policy outcome: AuScope geospatial data is used by scientists in academia and government to successfully make a policy case for updating the national geodetic datum by the end of the decade (2030), creating benefits for spatially sensitive industries, including construction, shipping, mining and agriculture through high-precision location information.¹
- A key commercial outcome: the Julimar deposit discovery by an industry geologist who used a Geoscience Australia map that included AuScope seismology data.²
- Ongoing community outcomes: delivering educational workshops in urban, regional and remote schools in Australia through the AuScope Seismometers In Schools (AuSIS) and other programs.³

Uncovering community insights

Between late 2023 and late 2024, AuScope engaged with more than 100 people across AuScope Communities from Australia and beyond - including Earth scientists, social scientists, Indigenous scientists, citizen scientists, chief scientists and more - to help build this Strategy.

These AuScope Communities include:

- The AuScope team, including the Board of Directors, HQ and Project delivery teams
- AuScope NCRIS Project collaborators
- Researchers at all career levels in academia (including in universities and publicly-funded research agencies like Geoscience Australia)
- Policy makers, including DE and chief scientists
- Government scientists at all career levels
- Industry scientists at all career levels in mining, technical services and consultancy industries
- Media professionals working for diverse outlets
- Indigenous people and groups, including (active and emerging) Indigenous scientists, policy makers and Knowledge holders
- Educators and students in schools (Year 10 focus) and universities
- Peak bodies for geoscience and STEM broadly
- The general public, including citizen scientists

Common barriers

Through workshops and interviews with AuScope Community members, including in the CSIRO ON Prime 15 program⁴ (On Prime), AuScope uncovered both research translation barriers and potential solutions that people experience in relation to AuScope. Whilst each AuScope Community revealed distinct barriers, common barriers across all groups include:

- Inadequate capability and capacity
- Low awareness of the AuScope capability
- Inefficient access to AuScope capability particularly to complete national geoscience research data collections in a central place

1. AuScope (2018): <https://bit.ly/4g0AnKC>
 2. AuScope (2021): <https://bit.ly/38nsn8n>
 3. AuScope (2023): <https://bit.ly/3KvAP5s>
 4. CSIRO (2025): <https://bit.ly/4kCkTyk>

Images (Clockwise): AuScope team members admiring part of AuScope's very-long baseline interferometry (VLBI) radio telescope at the Mount Pleasant Radio Observatory on Paredaremerme Country; metalliferous ore of the Julimar Deposit on Whadjuk Noongar Country, and AuScope team members who participated in the CSIRO ON Prime 15 program in 2024 including (from left) Dr Rebecca Farrington, Dr Tim Rawling and Jo Condon on Wurundjeri Country.

Strategy on a page

1. CSIRO (2024): <https://vimeo.com/911516429>
2. NSW Government (2024): <https://bit.ly/3FBTE7L>
3. CSIRO (2024): <https://bit.ly/4jldF1h>

Vision:	Australia is a sustainable and resilient nation underpinned by responsible geoscientific research translation at AuScope.				
Mission:	To empower the AuScope team to transform its research outputs into impactful policy, business and community outcomes that align with national priorities. Research translation converts research outputs into policy, industry, and community outcomes. AuScope research outputs include instruments, data, software and knowledge. People can convert research outputs into outcomes through different Earth science applications, such as critical minerals discovery and recovery, groundwater characterisation, geohazard monitoring and modelling, and place-based education. AuScope or researcher users can lead this process. It can be active (with the AuScope team and users helping end-users gain value from AuScope for their policy, industry or community development work) or passive (with end-users finding and using AuScope research outputs independently). All pathways are valuable. The Australian Government guides AuScope's work through the 2021 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap (2022), Australia's National Science and Research Priorities (2024) and other key policies.				
Principles:	Anything is possible: With skill and creativity, anyone at AuScope can translate a basic or applied research output into valuable knowledge for anyone (scientist or non-scientists), anywhere, anytime.	Always better together: AuScope has the greatest impact by building trusted relationships with its collaborators, centring user and end-user needs, and generating mutually beneficial outcomes.	Problem-focussed: By deeply understanding the problem - with the person who experiences it - before exploring possible solutions, AuScope can streamline and maximise impactful outcomes.	Responsible innovation¹: Just because we can, doesn't mean we should. AuScope can minimise bias and maximise impactful research outcomes by ensuring diverse, inclusive and equitable research inputs.	Climate conscious: As climate change continues to reshape global systems, AuScope's work supports scalable, Earth science-driven and Indigenous-led ² responses that strengthen resilience to shocks across regions and sectors.

AuScope Communities & Research Translation Barriers:	Producers of AuScope research outputs in academia: The AuScope team and teams in AuScope's NCRIS peer organisations in academia can experience barriers like:	Users of AuScope research outputs in academia: Researchers in universities or publicly-funded research agencies (PFRAs) such as Geoscience Australia, CSIRO and the Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation (ANSTO) can experience barriers like:	End-users of AuScope research outputs in government: Scientists and policy makers in state or federal government agencies, including geological surveys, the Department of Education (DE), Cooperative Research Centres (CRCs) and Centres of Excellence (CoEs) can experience barriers like:	End-users of AuScope research outputs in industry: Scientists and non-scientists in key AuScope industries, including mining, technical services, consulting, media and other emerging industries (that AuScope may support in the future) can experience barriers like:	End-users of AuScope research outputs in community: Scientists and non-scientists in place- or interest-based communities, namely Indigenous, education, peak bodies, citizen science, NGOs and general public communities, can experience barriers like:
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Unclear TRI remit and absent incentives — Inadequate capability or capacity — A paucity of innovation culture — Inadequate evaluation practice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Low awareness of full AuScope capability, including national geoscience datasets and collaborative NRI development — Poor user experience and no/slow support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Low awareness and poor user experience — Confusion about AuScope complexity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Low awareness and poor user experience — Confusion about AuScope complexity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Low awareness of AuScope — Low/no capacity to unlock AuScope value — Low trust in institutions to deliver mutually beneficial outcomes through co-design

Priorities:	1: Build AuScope's capability	2: Grow awareness of AuScope	3: Increase uptake of AuScope	4: Increase end-user collaboration:	5: Evaluate AuScope activities
Goals:	To create a skilled research translation cohort across Auscope that values, routinely drives, and inspires equitable, real-world impact.	To inform potential users and collaborators in every sector about how AuScope can generate value for their and others' work.	To increase the usage (as distinct from users or the number of uses) and value of AuScope for users and potential users in every sector.	To increase strategic connection, collaboration, partnerships, and problem-solving between people across sectors and diverse domains.	To sustain routine, engaging and holistic evaluation practice at AuScope that drives increased value for users and end-users.
Actions Today:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Update AuScope governance and systems — Build HQ and Projects action plans — Build an AuScope community of practice — Grow research translation literacy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Align marketing and engagement priorities — User and end-user journey mapping — Where possible, promote AuScope widely — Fund high-value demonstration projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Review insights from ON Prime — Fix simple barriers from ON Prime — Continue uncovering ecosystem barriers — Offer more support for diverse uptake — Fund high-value demonstration projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Monitor ecosystem and priority shifts — Identify collaboration opportunities — Where possible, facilitate engagements — Fund high-value demonstration projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Adopt CSIRO's Impact Evaluation Guide³ — Apply across all AuScope TRI activities — Evaluate, showcase and plan improvements — Incentivise evaluation practice with funding
Actions With Investment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Undertake training and share knowledge — Engage specialist/deep domain expertise — Fund high-value demonstration projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Deliver bespoke communications products — Routinely deliver bespoke engagements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Investigate more complex barriers — Scope potential collaborative projects to address more complex barriers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Routinely facilitate engagements — Undertake strategic knowledge brokering 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Deepen TRI evaluation practice — Expand evaluation practice across all NRI activities, not only TRI activities — Commission independent evaluation
Outcomes, Year-On-Year:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Increased specialist skills across the team — Increased research translation activities — A stronger sovereign research capability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Increased awareness of AuScope — Increased trust in AuScope — Increased trust in geoscience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Increased uptake of AuScope by users — Increased uptake of AuScope by end-users — Increased issues resolution across AuScope 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Increased value sharing across sectors — Increased value sharing across domains — Increased industry investment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Identified successes across activities — Identified improvements across AuScope — Actioned improvements across AuScope

Priority 1: Build AuScope's capability

The AuScope team experiences a range of strategic, capability, capacity, education, culture, and evaluation-related barriers to research translation, many of which are also common across the NCRIS community.

By continuing to collaborate with our funder and NCRIS peers, strengthening internal systems, making space for knowledge sharing, and investing in training and expert guidance, AuScope creates foundations as a world-class translation research infrastructure capability.

The problem

AuScope is responsible for ensuring users and end-users are using - and maximising value from - AuScope NRI. It has been translating its research outputs into outcomes for almost two decades. However, the language of research translation is relatively new to AuScope's NCRIS context, gaining first prominence in the 2021 Roadmap.

Consequently, the components of AuScope's TRI role require clarity to understand the extent to which it should serve users over end-users, different end-users over each other, or one industry over another in its work. AuScope seeks clarity on where its TRI role starts and ends with sector-specific research translation journeys across TRLs and SRLs.

Role uncertainties make resourcing research translation activities at AuScope challenging. Limiting mindsets like 'we don't have time to engage' or 'build it, and they will come' also contribute to the problem. The absence of robust evaluation practice, as per the CSIRO Impact Evaluation Guide¹, further compromises AuScope's capacity to drive continuous improvement and, therefore, greater impact. AuScope's evaluation barrier is explained and addressed in Priority 5 (Page 20).

AuScope's solutions

AuScope is already strengthening its research translation capability by defining our TRI role alongside our NCRIS peers and adjusting our NRI Project selection criteria, contracts, and reporting templates. Next, we will develop action plans for HQ and Projects, ensuring consistent priorities and direction for research translation. We will create a community of practice to build research translation literacy, skills, confidence, collaboration, knowledge sharing, and action using best practices across our team and Projects. Where possible, we will share knowledge with the broader research and innovation community in Australia and beyond.

With future investment, AuScope can engage experts to help us develop skills in human-centred design^{2,3} (mainly product and service design), engagement⁴, business development, marketing, communications, software development and Indigenous cultural capability⁵. We can also grow the AuScope team and incentivise responsible research translation through the AuScope Opportunity Fund and other activities.

Outcomes from these actions include more thoughtful and impactful systems and plans that support a skilled and passionate team in shaping and delivering best practices in research translation. Ultimately, this means a more resilient, sovereign research capability for Australia.

Photo by Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN)

Above: AuScope team member Dr Graeme Beardsmore and his University of Melbourne collaborator Belay Gulte Mino at the Melbourne Connect Co-Working Space on Wurundjeri Country. Graeme is passionate about exploring Australia's geothermal potential and sharing knowledge with emerging scientists worldwide.

"For me, job satisfaction comes from research translation so this is something I want to push. I am confident that researchers and industry will find value in AuScope heat flow equipment and tools if the equipment and tools are easily accessible and usable. Online tools and database will be easy to access, but field and laboratory equipment require skilled and experienced operators. Infrastructure is of little value if there is nobody to operate and maintain it!"

Dr Graeme Beardsmore, AuScope team member

1. CSIRO Impact Evaluation Guide (2024): <https://bit.ly/4jldF1h>
2. Australian Government - Human Centred Design (2025): <https://bit.ly/42pb8gk>
3. Victorian Government - Human Centred Design (2025): <https://bit.ly/3yxdFpt>
4. Training with IAP2 Australasia (2025): <https://iap2.org.au/training/>
5. Diversity Council Australia (2025): <https://bit.ly/4kzrEBf>

Priority 2: Grow awareness of AuScope

Current and potential users and end-users of AuScope commonly experience awareness and communications barriers to research translation with AuScope.

By aligning our marketing and engagement priorities, mapping user and end-user journeys, amplifying marketing efforts where possible, funding high-value demonstration projects, and investing in bespoke communications and engagements, AuScope can increase uptake by diverse users and end-users.

Photo by Poliana Vidal

The problem

Unsurprisingly, the closer someone is to Australia's Earth and geospatial science research ecosystem, the more likely they are to know and gain value from AuScope. In academia, researchers based in universities and publicly funded research agencies (PFRAs) like Geoscience Australia and CSIRO are mainly aware of AuScope. Still, they may not fully understand the full breadth of what AuScope offers or that AuScope invites their input into collaborative NRI development.

In government environments, such as state and territory geological surveys, scientists often know at least some of what AuScope offers since they may deliver AuScope NRI in their facilities and platforms. Policy makers, advisors and advocates may not know AuScope or NCRIS. They generally find it challenging to understand and communicate AuScope's complex capability and unique value within the broader research and Earth science ecosystem, including links with Geoscience Australia, CSIRO and state and territory geological surveys. Scientists in industry may not know AuScope, even if they access it through delivery partners.

Non-scientists in key AuScope industries are commonly unaware of AuScope. Still, they are happy to learn about its often openly accessible and sometimes bespoke offering. Similarly, people in place- and interest-based communities tend not to know about AuScope, only its much larger peers at Geoscience Australia, CSIRO, state and territory geological surveys and universities. They cannot often unlock any value from AuScope without assistance.

AuScope's solution

Now, AuScope aligns its internal marketing, communication, and engagement functions and priorities to address its key funder, user, and end-user group barriers. Next, AuScope will map key user and end-user journeys to understand and increase AuScope visibility across key brand touch points. AuScope will also provide opportunities for its team to undertake high-value promotional activities to benefit end-users. With further investment, AuScope can increase its capacity to develop and deliver bespoke communications products (like infographics, explainer videos and service catalogues) and engagement activities (including webinars and lectures), forging deeper awareness across user and end-user communities. Together, these actions will raise awareness of AuScope, build trust in the organisation, and strengthen public confidence and literacy in geoscience.

"I was familiar with AuScope but hadn't fully appreciated the wide range of tools, data, software, and expertise that AuScope provides for researchers like me. For instance, I'm particularly excited to learn about EarthBank [formerly AusGeochem], which will be incredibly valuable for translating my research into teaching and industry applications. It's also great to discover the AuScope Opportunity Fund, which supports researchers in testing ideas that address national research infrastructure needs. I'm especially grateful that AuScope delivered an awareness-raising lecture for my colleagues at the University of Tasmania during a visit to Hobart shortly after I suggested the idea."

Dr Francisco Testa, University of Tasmania

Left: Dr Francisco Testa explains the science of sedimentology to school students at Kingston beach on Palawa / Pakana Country.

Priority 3: Increase uptake of AuScope

AuScope users and end-users experience data, communications, support and culture-related barriers to research translation with AuScope. By focusing on user and end-user needs in our work, funding high-value demonstration projects, and investing in collaborative investigation of complex barriers, AuScope can increase usage towards policy, industry, and community outcomes.

The problem

Users and end-users need to access data and other research capabilities around Australia quickly and seamlessly. If they encounter access or user experience barriers, they may disengage without seeking help. Both scientists and non-scientists have unique needs, workflows and communication styles. Assumptions about their needs and barriers in NRI development can significantly limit uptake. Support, when required, is crucial to augment a smooth user experience. Community end-users, particularly Indigenous and regional and remote groups, can benefit from supported and culturally sensitive engagement with AuScope to build geoscience literacy on Country, about Country. Indigenous people also require protections to ensure they benefit from AuScope research outputs with free, prior and informed consent, as per the AIATSIS Code of Ethics¹ (as per the 2021 Roadmap, which guides AuScope's NRI work). Finally, some communities experience trust barriers to engaging with AuScope due to distrust in government institutions² and industry³.

AuScope's solution

AuScope is already reviewing and addressing insights from ON Prime. Next, we will address CARE⁴ and FAIR⁵ data barriers through the new AuScope Research Data Systems Strategy 2025 - 30⁶. We will also attune to the AIATSIS Code of Ethics and the Our Knowledge, Our Way guidelines⁷ to build protocols for engagement for AuScope, and protocols to protect Indigenous Knowledges (as per the 2021 Roadmap). We will uncover new ecosystem barriers and offer more timely, seamless and culturally sensitive support for diverse users by undertaking training (see Priority 1), communicating clearly, and being guided by user and end-user needs. We will also fund high-value demonstration projects - guided by mutual AuScope, user and end-user needs - through the AuScope Opportunity Fund. With further investment, AuScope can investigate and tackle more complex barriers to AuScope uptake across entities and jurisdictions nationally, with new and existing partners. These actions will drive high-value uptake of AuScope.

“Indigenous people are often required to fit into the research programs long after the research questions and methodologies are developed, and then sought after to assist the researcher to answer their questions. My experiences have led me to flip the paradigm to seek my peoples' questions they wish to have answered through research. Removing the power imbalance in the research question, the co-production then has more chance to benefit the Indigenous people; this is a small step in the right direction, if achieved. The beginning of a broader shift to address power imbalances in research, such as moving to an Indigenous Research Methodology that is culturally appropriate, to leading as co-authors, co-presenting at conferences and leading to co-benefit.”⁸

Professor Brad Moggridge, Kamileroi Scientist, University of Technology Sydney

One of the risks in delivering data and knowledge is you sometimes have an 'if they build it, they will come' mentality, particularly in research. Blue Sky research is acceptable, but for data delivery platforms, this is not appropriate. What are all the other data sets and data platform options that users must interface with? Having the 'voice of the customer' in AuScope NRI development and delivery is very important. Products must be useful, usable and used. For example, when we observe problems with information in subsurface models at BHP, we do a 'Gemba Walk': we step through the model development and delivery process with everyone involved - to identify improvements.

Dr Cam McCuaig, AuScope Board Member / Head of Generative Exploration at BHP

Image by Jo Condon

Pictured: AuScope team member and University of Melbourne lecturer Dr Hayden Dalton using the AuScope supported EarthBank (formerly AusGeochem) platform on Wurunderji Country. Hayden is passionate about sharing his geochemistry knowledge, the power of AuScope tools like EarthBank, and Earth science careers with university students, school students and Indigenous communities.

1. AIATSIS (2020): <https://bit.ly/3Hg7mxM>
2. The Conversation (2017): <https://bit.ly/4iKGwL4>
3. CSIRO (2021): <https://bit.ly/3S1r02w>
4. Global Indigenous Data Alliance (2025): <https://bit.ly/4joVirl>
5. Australian Research Data Commons (2025): <https://bit.ly/43RGifO>
6. AuScope (2025): www.auscope.org.au/strategy
7. CSIRO (2020): <https://bit.ly/3Ygl064>
8. Springer Nature Link (2024): <https://bit.ly/3SZZfaZ>

Priority 4: Increase end-user collaboration

Capacity, communication, and culture-related barriers are common for AuScope Communities as they ‘hand the baton over’. By identifying, supporting, and growing inclusive engagements, funding high-value demonstration projects, and investing in knowledge brokering services, AuScope can create an innovative research translation capability based on trusted relationships.

The problem

End-user engagement is a new and growing focus for AuScope, creating opportunities to bring its communities together to tackle shared challenges and support national priorities. Many people within AuScope and its wider network are passionate about collaboration but need support to start, build, and maintain trusted partnerships. They also need help building relationships, communicating, sharing knowledge, and making decisions together across different areas of expertise and cultures. This includes with Indigenous people and groups who seek inclusion science, and answers to their questions about their lands, waters and skies. Critically, engagement must commence from the start to the end of NRI projects, to make sure the end product is culturally safe for consumption.

AuScope’s solution

By identifying strategic collaboration opportunities, supporting inclusive engagement, and funding key demonstration projects through the AuScope Opportunity Fund, AuScope can quickly grow its network and impact today. With further investment, it can support community-led engagement and offer knowledge brokering services. This will boost two-way knowledge creation across sectors, fields, and cultures, including place-based education to help care for Country and improve geoscience literacy within Indigenous communities. It will also help AuScope attract more industry and government investment - demonstrating mutual goals in action - and strengthening national resilience to climate change, natural disasters, geopolitical tensions, rapid technology changes, and competition for resources and supply chains.

Collaboration needs to be faster and more intentional. Collaboration is essential: researchers, industry, and government must work together more effectively. We must encourage early collaboration between researchers, investors, and technology transfer offices to align priorities. Collaboration enhances innovation – structured group exercises like ‘Yes, and’ help expand thinking rather than dismissing ideas. Casual and safe environments foster collaboration, as does active listening. Authentic partnerships require deep engagement – true collaboration with Indigenous communities is about listening first, honouring cultural protocols, and building relationships before pursuing research or commercialisation.

Key ‘collaboration’ messages from speakers at ON Core 2025¹ event in Meanjin, collated by CSIRO

“Reflecting on the [AuScope supported JOIDES Resolution Academy 2024] journey, I am in awe of what can happen when passion meets possibility. As a young girl, I would have never dreamed that I’d one day sail on a research vessel, supporting a group of brilliant young science students from across the world, passionate about social and climate justice. To climb Mt Vesuvius with a volcanologist, create Pūtangitangi flutes, and share traditional scientific knowledge passed through generations alongside new brothers and sisters - this experience is beyond what my grandmother and mother could have imagined. They were with me in spirit when I saw my two totems - dolphin and whale, out at sea after facilitating a weaving circle.

These experiences remind me that the world truly is our oyster - as Indigenous leaders who have so much to gift industry, society, beyond. and so much to gain by walking alongside one another and sharing observations, hopes, stories of determination and strength.”

Ann-Maree Long

Pictured (from left): AuScope HQ team members touring the HyLogger facility at Mineral Resources Tasmania on Palawa/Pakana Country; Dr Jess Stromberg from CSIRO presenting a HyLogger workshop for industry at the Sustainable Minerals Institute on Turrbal and Yuggera Country; Indigenous mentor Ann-Maree Long on board the JOIDES Resolution research vessel in European waters in the JR Academy.

1. CSIRO (2021): <https://bit.ly/44kdRct>

Priority 5: Evaluate AuScope activities

How did we do? By adopting and incentivising robust evaluation practices today and deepening our efforts with more significant investment in the future, AuScope can better articulate - and celebrate - its impacts and drive meaningful change to support AuScope Communities.

The problem

AuScope undertakes routine statutory reporting on its NRI activities, which includes counts of TRI users, end-users and usage, and surveying. However, it has not yet adopted a formal, holistic evaluation framework to measure progress, drive continuous improvement, support storytelling and help cultivate an impact-oriented culture. Without robust evaluation of AuScope NRI and TRI activities, AuScope cannot gain critical insights into its successes, challenges, user experience and growth opportunities. An essential aspect of this evaluation will be for representatives of all AuScope Communities to evaluate AuScope's work independently. Further, without consistent evaluation-related language, AuScope cannot accurately articulate or benchmark success, set clear goals, or track its progress effectively.

AuScope's solution

Today, AuScope can adopt CSIRO's Impact Evaluation Guide¹, test it across HQ and Project TRI initiatives, undertake annual evaluation and planning sessions, and encourage evaluation by providing funding opportunities to further TRI activities. With more investment, AuScope can strengthen its TRI and NRI evaluation activities and commission independent evaluations. These actions will help strengthen AuScope's capacity to identify successes and areas for improvement and, in doing so, help foster a culture of impact and innovation.

"If I could have one wish granted, it would be to stop the clock at the start of the project so that we can better plan how we're going to engage with the beneficiaries of our research outputs before, during and after their production. We're so delivery-focused that we often rush to the next project without thinking deeply about legacy and ongoing value creation."

AuScope geoscience community member

Pictured, top right: AuScope team member and seismologist at the Australian National University, Dr Sima Mousavi teaching school students at Hawkesdale P - 12 College about geoscience, on Eastern Maar Country. Bottom right: wind towers on Menang Country.

1. CSIRO (2024): <https://bit.ly/4jldF1h>

Implementing this Strategy

Next, it's time for action! Over the next five years, we will collaborate across AuScope Communities to scope, deliver and evaluate initiatives in response to the Priorities, Actions and Outcomes of this Strategy. Together, we can take creative pathways to drive responsible solutions to national priorities.

Turning ideas into action

Many members of AuScope Communities have shared a range of possible solutions - small and large - to help overcome their barriers to research translation with AuScope. Some of these ideas are pictured in yellow sticky notes here. The AuScope team, at HQ and in Project teams, is now tasked with considering these possible solutions while generating initiatives in response to this Strategy.

Help us bring this Strategy to life

We invite AuScope Communities to help bring this Strategy to life, and to evolve it over time. Whether you are an AuScope team member, user, or end-user, or would like to be, please email us at info@auscope.org.au if you would like to help shape, deliver or evaluate AuScope initiatives.

Idea:
Place-based education that helps us care for Country.

Idea:
Collaboration spaces that enable us to share and innovate across domains, sectors and cultures.

Idea:
Genuine co-design practice to remove power asymmetry and ensure mutually beneficial outcomes.

Idea:
One place for all data that everyone understands.

Idea:
Budget that allows us to fail, as per NASA!

Above: Australia's National Science and Research Priorities (2024) - featuring Aboriginal and/or Torres Strait Islander knowledge systems at the centre - which help guide AuScope's NRI and TRI activities. Image: Department of Industry, Science and Resources.

Photo by Ezra Alcantra Photography

Photo by Rory O'Sullivan, Chorus

Photo by Vlad Alekseev

Pictured (left): Curtin University PhD student Silva Joseph speaking during a John de Laeter Centre tour with Government of WA decision makers on Whadjuk Noongar Country; seismologists Dr Voon Hui Lai, Professor Meghan Miller and Professor John Townend on Māori Whenua; and university students at the CAGE24 geophysics camp at Katter Kich (Wave Rock) on Nyaki-Nyaki Country.

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